

PHYTOCHEMICAL STUDY OF QUINCE FRUITS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17337465>

Relevance:

Quince (*Cydonia oblonga*) is a valuable source of vitamins, micro- and macroelements, as well as phenolic compounds and flavonoids. The biologically active substances of quince exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and tonic effects, making it a promising object of phytochemical research. Studying the chemical composition of quince fruits is relevant for substantiating their application in medicine, dietology, and the food industry.

Aim of the research: Phytochemical study of quince fruits (*Cydonia oblonga*) with the determination of water-soluble vitamins, microelements, and phenolic compounds.

Materials and methods: The research object was ripe quince fruits (*Cydonia oblonga*).

The following methods were applied:

- high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) - to determine the vitamin content;
- atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) - to study the microelement composition;
- spectrophotometry-for quantitative analysis of phenolic compounds and flavonoids.

All analyses were carried out in triplicate, and the results were statistically processed.

Results: Quince fruits were found to have a high content of vitamin C (up to 15 mg/100 g) and smaller amounts of B vitamins.

-Microelements identified: iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), manganese (Mn), and copper (Cu).

-The presence of flavonoids and phenolic compounds with pronounced antioxidant activity was established.

Conclusions: Conducting a phytochemical study of quince fruits (*Cydonia oblonga*), I became convinced of their rich composition. I was impressed by the high content of vitamins, microelements, and phenolic compounds. This confirms the unique properties of quince and substantiates its use in medicine and dietology as a valuable natural source of biologically active substances.